

Geostructural Liquefaction Assessment of a Road Embankment Foundation

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Abstract— Liquefaction is one of the destructive hazards that affects the infrastructural foundation of buildings, dams, embankments, roads, and bridges. The liquefaction assessment should be conducted before construction of the infrastructure to determine and mitigate any liquefiable soil layer underneath the foundation. The research work aimed to address the soil liquefaction potential of the proposed road embankment foundation, which is located along the coastal area of Navotas City. The embankment foundation has a total cross-sectional area of two hundred fifty-two (252) square meters. A geostructural-based method was adopted in the research study to understand and evaluate the different liquefaction-related parameters that can contribute to the hazard during an earthquake event. The screening-based method for fine-grained soil proposed by Bray and Sancho (2006), in parallel with the simplified liquefaction-based procedure developed by Youd and Idriss (2001), was used in the liquefaction analysis. The account for the variabilities in the data parameters, the minimum acceptable values for the factor of safety considered in the research work were 1.25. The results showed that the upper soil layer with a thickness of 3 m to 4 m will liquefy under a 7.5 magnitude earthquake. The computed safety factor ranges from 0.2507 to 1.0010. Moreover, the geostructural performance assessment showed that the liquifiable soil layer will cause a differential displacement of 1.13 m to 1.36 m and tilting of around 4.08° to 4.89° to the embankment foundation. Cost-effective mitigating measures should be implemented as the research study considered the use of a stone column encased with geosynthetic material. This ground improvement stabilization method provides densification, drainage, and reinforcement to the subsurface soil layer, which provides a long-term solution against soil liquefaction.

Keywords: embankment foundation, geostructural approach, soil liquefaction, factor of safety, mitigation, ground improvement technique, stone column

I. INTRODUCTION

Liquefaction is one of the hazards that might affect the structural integrity of any infrastructural foundation. During an earthquake, loose saturated cohesionless soils tend to collapse and liquefy due to the reduced strength and stiffness brought by the effect of seismic ground motion. Numerous researchers in the Philippines conducted comprehensive studies about seismic hazards, and they often show that the country has a high level of seismicity, which may produce an earthquake with a large moment magnitude greater than seven [1].

In the assessment of liquefaction, several geotechnical data points are needed, such as percent of fines, depth of the soil layers, groundwater level, soil type, SPT N-blows, and soil bulk density [2]. Basically, in conducting liquefaction potential assessment, two approaches can be used, namely deterministic analysis and probabilistic analysis. Between the two approaches, deterministic analysis is used mostly by engineers to examine the liquefaction hazard in soil based on semi-empirical correlations [3].

The research work was conducted to provide proper mitigation of the soil liquefaction hazard that might affect the proposed road embankment foundation. The proposed site for the construction of the road embankment foundation is located in the coastal area of Navotas City, within the National Capital Region of the Philippines. The embankment foundation has a cross-sectional area of two hundred fifty-two (252) square meters.

The main objective of this research is to assess and mitigate the soil liquefaction hazard for the proposed road embankment foundation by evaluating the factor of safety and analyzing the earthquake-induced liquefaction parameters through a geostructural approach.

Specifically, this study was undertaken to address the following objectives:

1. Identify and classify the various earthquake-induced liquefaction parameters that may contribute to the liquefaction risk of the embankment foundation;
2. Analyze the cyclic shear strength of the subsoil and the cyclic shear stress induced by earthquake loading, using the liquefaction triggering method based on Standard Penetration Test (SPT) data;
3. Analyze the cyclic shear strength of the subsoil and the cyclic shear stress induced by earthquake loading, using the liquefaction triggering method based on Standard Penetration Test (SPT) data;
4. Determine the depth of liquefiable soil based on the analysis of geostructural results and evaluate the inducing upward total buoyant force, subgrade modulus of reaction, differential displacement, and potential tilting of the embankment foundation; and,
5. Develop an appropriate mitigation plan to address the soil liquefaction hazard impacting the embankment foundation.

One aspect of analyzing the integrity of the foundation is to withstand any seismic-related events. In line with this, each earthquake-induced parameter was investigated properly to visualize the subsurface conditions of the study area and to better understand which of these parameters may contribute to the liquefaction risk of the embankment foundation. The geostructural factors that serve as the key concept in

evaluating soil liquefaction were combined to derive a precise countermeasure to the liquefiable soil layers. Proper judgment and accurate recommendations, including mitigating techniques, must be provided to attain a strong embankment foundation that is not susceptible to liquefaction.

The central focus of the research work is the evaluation of the liquefiable soil layer beneath the proposed road embankment foundation, which is in Navotas City, Metro Manila. The scope of research study comprised the estimation of the CRR, CSR, and safety factor (FS) using the simplified procedure method developed by Youd and Idriss (2001) [4]. This research work was limited to the use of available collected data, such as seismic data, geotechnical borehole data, and structural data provided by the Department of Science and Technology - Philippine Institute of Volcanology and Seismology (DOST-PHIVOLCS) and KE Asia Inc.

II. METHODOLOGY

There are different stages of the process in conducting the geotechnical liquefaction potential assessment. These stages are greatly examined to produce an excellent and valuable result. In the research study, there were three (3) phases considered in evaluating the liquefaction susceptibility of the soil and its effect on the proposed road embankment foundation.

Phase 1. Identification of Earthquake-Induced Liquefaction Parameters

The earthquake-induced parameters are the fundamental data in assessing the liquefaction susceptibility of the embankment foundation. It is important to understand the initiation process of these parameters concerning liquefaction. These parameters include both geotechnical and structural data. The structural data is primarily based on the width, thickness, and depth of the embankment foundation. The geotechnical data will come from the results of the geotechnical investigation and subsurface borehole logs, including but not limited to the geological data and seismic data. The combination of the two (2) data serves as the output of the research phase 1.

Phase 2: Geotechnical Liquefaction Assessment

The liquefaction triggering method adopted in the study is based on the simplified procedure approach. In this method, input parameters from the borehole log data were used in computing the cyclic resistance ratio (CRR) value, magnitude scaling factor (MSF), the value of cyclic stress ratio (CSR), stress reduction coefficient, peak ground acceleration, total vertical stress, and effective pressure. The final output will be the value of the factor of safety (FS), which will be used to recognize the liquefiable layer. Moreover, the geotechnical assessment was done to determine the uplift stability and deformation against structural limits of the foundation by calculating the buoyant uplift forces, subgrade modulus of reaction, differential displacement, and tilting of the embankment.

In the research work, the value of CRR is standardized to a 7.5 design earthquake magnitude. The seismic magnitude value is based on the highest possible earthquake scenario that might happen on the site. The following expression can be used in evaluating the CRR:

$$CRR_M = \frac{1}{34 - (N_1)_{60cs}} + \frac{(N_1)_{60cs}}{135} + \frac{50}{[10(N_1)_{60cs} + 45]^2} - \frac{1}{200} \times MSF$$

Where:

$(N_1)_{60cs}$ = corrected N-value

MSF = magnitude scaling factor

The CSR will be determined using this equation:

$$CSR = 0.65 \left[\left(\frac{a_{max}}{g} \right) \times \left(\frac{\sigma_{vo}}{\sigma'_{vo}} \right) \right] \times r_d$$

Where:

a_{max} = gravity acceleration, $\frac{m}{s^2}$

σ_{vo} = total vertical stress, *kPa*

σ'_{vo} = effective vertical stress, *kPa*

r_d = stress reduction coefficient

The FS of each layered soil is estimated carefully using two (2) defined values, the CSR and CRR. To estimate the value of the safety factor, the CRR will be divided by the CSR. In practice, if the resulting value of FS is equal to or less than 1, then it is considered liquefiable; otherwise, if it is greater than 1, then it is not liquefiable. The acceptable range value of the FS considered in this research study is from 1.25 to 1.5. It means that if the safety factor value of the soil layer is less than 1.25, then it is liquefiable.

$$FS = \frac{CRR}{CSR}$$

Where:

CRR = cyclic resistance ratio

CSR = cyclic stress ratio

The induced upward buoyant force is primarily due to the increase in pore water pressure from the liquefied soil beneath the embankment. The equation used to calculate the total upward buoyant force acting on the embankment is given below:

$$F_b = (\gamma_w)(Area)(H_{liq})$$

Where:

γ_w = unit weight of water, $\frac{kN}{m^3}$

Area = embankment area, m^2

H_{liq} = total thickness of liquefied soil layers, *m*

The subgrade modulus represents the stiffness of the soil beneath the embankment and is a key parameter in determining foundation deformation under load. The equation used to determine the modulus of subgrade reaction under non-liquefied soil conditions is given below:

$$k_s = \frac{E_s}{B}$$

Where:

E_s = soil elastic modulus, *kPa*

B = width of the embankment, *m*

When parts of the embankment experience different amounts of uplift or settlement, differential displacement usually occurs, leading to tilting of the foundation. The tilt angle of the embankment can be determined using the equation below:

$$\theta = \tan^{-1} \left(\frac{\Delta\delta}{L} \right)$$

Where:

$\Delta\delta$ = total differential displacement, *m*

L = length of the embankment, *m*

Phase 3: Mitigation Design and Ground Improvement Techniques

Every liquefiable soil layer must be mitigated to prevent any structural damage to the foundation. The soil layer that tends to liquefy based on geotechnical evaluation should be identified and mitigated. The output of phase 2 will be the input of phase 3 in identifying the liquefiable and non-liquefiable layers. Both results of the geotechnical and structural approaches will be incorporated in the final selection of mitigation. The different input parameters of the two approaches will serve as the basis of selection concerning their impact on causing liquefaction. The output of phase 3 will recommend the most suited countermeasure for the potential liquefaction hazard that might affect the embankment foundation.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Specific Objective 1:

Identify and classify the various earthquake-induced liquefaction parameters that may contribute to the liquefaction risk of the embankment foundation.

Site Geological Data

The lithology of the study area is identified to be part of the Manila Formation (MGB, 2010). Based on the geologic map presented in Figure 1, the study area lies within the Quaternary Alluvium. These unconsolidated alluvial deposits comprise various soil materials, including silt, clay, gravelly sand, and tuffaceous silt.

Figure 1. Geologic map of the study area (MGB, 2010)

Tectonics and Seismicity

The nearest active fault within the study area is the West Valley Fault (Figure 2). Based on the PHIVOLCS Fault Finder, the West Valley Fault is approximately 15 km away from the study area. Moreover, the peak ground acceleration (PGA) of the study area is measured using the attenuation relationship equation of Fukushima and Tanaka, and the results are presented in Table 1. The earthquake magnitude considered in the analysis is 7.5, which has generated a peak ground acceleration of 0.4053 g. A correction factors are applied in the calculation depending on the type of soil material obtained in the area.

Figure 2. Distribution of active faults within the study area (PHIVOLCS, 2025)

Table 1. Estimated site-specific Peak Ground Acceleration (PGA) values

$\text{Log}_{10} A = 0.41M - \log_{10} (R + 0.032 \times 10^{0.41M}) - 0.0034R + 1.30$				
West Valley Fault	Magnitude, M		Distance, R	
	7.5		15 km	
<i>g</i>	<i>Rock (0.6g)</i>	<i>Hard soil (0.87g)</i>	<i>Medium soil (1.07g)</i>	<i>Soft soil (1.39g)</i>
0.405314745	0.243188847	0.352623828	0.433686777	0.563387496

Geotechnical Borehole Data

A total of six (6) boreholes were drilled in the study area (Figure 3). The boreholes have a total depth of 21 m NGL. The majority of the soil materials in the study area are classified as silty sand, silty sand with gravel, clayey sand, clayey sand with gravel, sandy silt, silt with sand, elastic silt, sandy clay, lean clay, lean clay with sand, and fat clay.

Figure 3. Borehole Location Map (Google, 2025)

Geometric Dimension Design

The embankment has a top width of 24 m, base width of 60 m, vertical height of 6 m, and side slope ratio of 1:3 (Figure 4). The cross-sectional area of the embankment is calculated to be 252 m². The total ground pressure exerted by the road embankment was measured to be 190 $\frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}^2}$.

Figure 4. Proposed geometric dimension design of the road embankment

Specific Objective 2:

Analyze the cyclic shear strength of the subsoil and the cyclic shear stress induced by earthquake loading, using the liquefaction triggering method based on Standard Penetration Test (SPT) data.

Cyclic Stress Ratio (CSR)

The cyclic stress ratio experienced by the soil as a result of a seismic loading was computed and presented in Table 2. Based on the results, the CSR value of the six (6) boreholes ranges from 0.2584 to 0.4732, with the highest calculated CSR value observed in BH-01 at depth 4.5 m NGL to 6.0 m NGL. Three (3) primary factors affect the CSR value: the peak ground acceleration (PGA), stress reduction factor, and the effective stress of the soil. As the PGA value increases, the CSR value also increases due to the greater seismic load that is being applied to the soil.

Table 2. Summary of the Calculated Cyclic Stress Ratio Value

Depth (m)							
Start	End	BH-01	BH-02	BH-03	BH-04	BH-05	BH-06
0.00	1.50	-	0.3620	-	0.3620	-	0.3620
1.50	3.00	0.3578	0.3578	0.3578	0.3736	-	0.3578
3.00	4.50	0.4122	0.3749	0.3536	0.4541	-	0.3693
4.50	6.00	0.4732	0.3316	0.4374	-	-	-
6.00	7.50	0.3897	0.2968	0.3735	0.4156	-	-
7.50	9.00	0.4129	0.3167	0.3275	0.3477	-	-
9.00	10.50	0.4116	-	0.3294	0.3508	0.3245	-
10.50	12.00	0.4044	-	0.3304	0.3479	-	-
12.00	13.50	0.3991	0.3217	-	0.3418	0.3245	0.4022
13.50	15.00	0.3130	-	0.3167	-	0.3190	0.3206
15.00	16.50	0.3008	-	0.3084	-	-	0.3057
16.50	18.00	0.2870	0.2991	-	-	-	0.2921
18.00	19.50	0.2730	0.2878	0.2837	0.3004	-	0.2813
19.50	21.00	0.2584	0.2745	0.2679	0.2858	-	-

Moreover, as seen in Table 3, the stress reduction factor decreases with depth while the effective vertical stress increases. The decrease in the stress reduction factor is due to

the flexibility of the soils, which causes the shear wave amplitude to diminish with depth. Furthermore, the increase in the effective vertical stress is due to the weight of the overlying soils, which is also the primary reason why the SPT N-values obtained are highest as we go deeper. The combined effect of a decreasing stress reduction factor and an increasing effective vertical stress at depth leads to a lower cyclic stress ratio at greater depths, which makes the soil much more resistant to soil liquefaction.

Table 3. Calculated Value of PGA, Stress Reduction Factor, and Effective Vertical Stress for BH-01

Depth (m)		Corrected Peak Ground Acceleration	Stress Reduction Factor	Effective Vertical Stress (kPa)
Start	End			
0.00	1.50	-	-	-
1.50	3.00	0.5634	0.9771	22.5000
3.00	4.50	0.5634	0.9656	44.2500
4.50	6.00	0.5634	0.9541	59.1900
6.00	7.50	0.4337	0.9426	69.2250
7.50	9.00	0.4337	0.9312	84.1350
9.00	10.50	0.4337	0.8937	94.1700
10.50	12.00	0.4337	0.8536	108.3300
12.00	13.50	0.4337	0.8136	122.4900
13.50	15.00	0.3526	0.7735	132.5250
15.00	16.50	0.3526	0.7335	147.4350
16.50	18.00	0.3526	0.6934	161.5950
18.00	19.50	0.3526	0.6534	176.5050
19.50	21.00	0.3526	0.6133	190.6650

Cyclic Resistance Ratio (CRR)

The cyclic resistance ratio, which represents the soil's resistance capacity to liquefaction during seismic shaking, was computed and presented in Table 4. Based on the results, the CRR value of the six (6) boreholes ranges from 0.1186 to 4.0593, with the highest calculated CRR value observed in BH-04. The CRR value is highly dependent on the corrected SPT N-values of the soil, which measure the direct soil resistance to penetration. A higher corrected SPT N-value generally indicates a greater resistance to soil liquefaction and thus, a higher CRR value.

Moreover, as seen in Table 4, a higher CRR value was observed at greater depths than in the shallower portion of the borehole. This indicates that the soil in the bottom part has a greater liquefaction resistance. This interpretation was further supported by the increase in the corrected SPT N-values and effective vertical stress measured at greater depths. The corrected SPT N-values, effective vertical stress, and CRR values are all directly proportional to one another.

Table 4. Summary of the Calculated Cyclic Resistance Ratio Value

Depth (m)		BH-01	BH-02	BH-03	BH-04	BH-05	BH-06
Start	End						
0.00	1.50	-	0.6711	-	0.1931	-	0.6711
1.50	3.00	0.3539	0.1958	0.1958	0.1954	-	0.1958
3.00	4.50	0.2966	0.3739	0.3539	4.0593	-	0.1724
4.50	6.00	0.1186	1.0812	0.3934	-	-	-
6.00	7.50	0.7208	2.0181	1.0180	1.1489	-	-
7.50	9.00	1.0810	2.5372	2.1954	1.5005	-	-
9.00	10.50	0.9131	-	2.5155	2.3631	1.9187	-
10.50	12.00	0.5695	-	2.4530	2.1673	-	-
12.00	13.50	1.2700	2.2499	-	2.2603	2.2861	1.3782
13.50	15.00	1.7853	-	2.2153	-	2.2016	1.5905
15.00	16.50	1.8127	-	2.1296	-	-	1.7267
16.50	18.00	1.4141	2.0234	-	-	-	1.8641
18.00	19.50	1.7871	1.9568	1.9530	1.9647	-	1.9095
19.50	21.00	1.7085	1.8895	1.8354	1.8968	-	-

Specific Objective 3:

Evaluate the subsoil safety factor and examine if it is within the acceptable range of values.

Factor of Safety (FS)

The factor of safety represents the ratio of the strength of the soil material to the actual working seismic stress it will experience during an earthquake. Due to the variability in the soil parameters, the minimum FS considered in the research study is 1.25. An FS lower than the acceptable value of 1.25 will undergo soil liquefaction during a seismic event.

Based on the results as seen in Table 5, the FS value of the six (6) boreholes, which is lower than the acceptable value of 1.25 is ranges from 0.2507 to 1.0010, with the lowest calculated CRR value observed in BH-01. Furthermore, a higher FS was observed at the lower portion of the borehole. The higher FS corresponds to the higher CRR value calculated at greater depths. This implies that as the value of CRR increases, the FS also increases, resulting in a higher soil resistance against liquefaction.

Table 5. Summary of the Calculated Factor of Safety Value

Depth (m)		BH-01	BH-02	BH-03	BH-04	BH-05	BH-06
Start	End						
0.00	1.50	-	1.8540	-	0.5333	-	1.8540
1.50	3.00	0.9892	0.5473	0.5473	0.5232	-	0.5473
3.00	4.50	0.7195	0.9974	1.0010	8.9402	-	0.4667
4.50	6.00	0.2507	3.2601	0.8993	-	-	-
6.00	7.50	1.8498	6.8001	2.7256	2.7647	-	-
7.50	9.00	2.6181	8.0106	6.7040	4.3156	-	-

9.00	10.50	2.2185	-	7.6361	6.7356	5.9137	-
10.50	12.00	1.4081	-	7.4235	6.2302	-	-
12.00	13.50	3.1821	6.9939	-	6.6133	7.0454	3.4264
13.50	15.00	5.7048	-	6.9950	-	6.9016	4.9607
15.00	16.50	6.0266	-	6.9047	-	-	5.6489
16.50	18.00	4.9270	6.7657	-	-	-	6.3827
18.00	19.50	6.5454	6.8000	6.8833	6.5391	-	6.7889
19.50	21.00	6.6121	6.8824	6.8501	6.6372	-	-

Specific Objective 4:

Determine the depth of liquefiable soil based on the analysis of geotechnical results and evaluate the inducing upward total buoyant force, modulus of subgrade reaction, differential displacement, and potential tilting of the embankment foundation.

Depth of Liquefiable Soil

The liquefiable soil layer was determined based on the overall results of the liquefaction analysis and is presented in Figure 5. From the six (6) boreholes, the depth of liquefiable soil was observed from 0.0 m NGL to 6.0 m NGL, where BH-01 and BH-03 have the thickest liquefiable layer, measured to be 4.5 m thick. Moreover, there is no liquefiable soil layer observed in BH-05. The soil materials that are found to be liquefiable include clayey sand, sandy silt, and elastic silt.

Figure 5. Cross-sectional profile of the six (6) boreholes showing the depth of the liquefiable soil layer

This soil layer was seen to have low SPT N-values and a plasticity index. During earthquake shaking, the loose soil structure due to the low SPT N-values is prone to collapse and generate excessive pore water pressure. Likewise, the low plasticity index indicates that the soil does not have enough cohesive strength to resist liquefaction, and these non-plastic silts behave more like fine sand during seismic shaking. The combination of the two

factors makes these soil layers moderately to highly susceptible to liquefaction. This interpretation was further supported by the seismic hazard assessment published in the PHIVOLCS HazardHunter PH Program, which indicates that the area has a moderately high potential for seismic liquefaction.

Induced Upward Total Buoyant Force, Modulus of Subgrade Reaction, Differential Displacement, and Tilting

The geotechnical assessment was done to determine the actual performance of the embankment foundation when a certain soil layer liquefies. The results of different factors that were considered in the analysis are presented in Table 6. The induced upward total buoyant force was calculated to be in the range of 7,416.36 kN to 11,124.54 kN. The total embankment weight is 47,880 kN. Subtracting the total embankment weight from the measured total buoyant force gives us a net downward force in the range of 36,755.46 kN to 40,463.64 kN. Since the calculated net downward force is greater than the upward total buoyant force, the embankment foundation will not experience uplift during seismic shaking. In addition, the ratio of the buoyant force to the downward force is computed to be 18.33% to 30.27%. These percentage indicates that there is a significant reduction in the effective stress on the foundation soil, which means that the strength and stability of the soil beneath the embankment foundation are highly compromised, increasing the risk of failure even though the embankment won't float or uplift.

Table 6. Summary of the Calculated Induced Upward Total Buoyant Force, Modulus of Subgrade Reaction, Differential Displacement, and Tilting

Boreholes	Induced Upward Total Buoyant Force (kN)	Modulus of Subgrade Reaction (kPa/m)	Differential Displacement (m)	Tilting (°)
BH-01	11124.54	2498.57	1.36	4.89
BH-02	7416.36	2498.57	1.28	4.59
BH-03	11124.54	1665.72	1.13	4.08
BH-04	7416.36	2658.60	1.15	4.15
BH-05	-	-	-	-
BH-06	7416.36	2498.57	1.29	4.66

Moreover, the calculated modulus of subgrade reaction ranges from 1665.72 kPa/m to 2658.60 kPa/m, with the lowest measured value observed in BH-03. The low modulus of subgrade reaction observed in BH-03 indicates that the soil material is highly compressible and lacks stiffness to provide adequate support for the foundation. This was further supported by the low SPT N-values obtained on the upper portion of the borehole. Furthermore, the computed differential displacement and tilting of the embankment foundation range from 1.13 m to 1.36 m and 4.08° to 4.89°. This calculated value indicates that in a worst-case scenario, the embankment foundation will have a differential displacement of 1.36m, and it will tilt to around 4.89° during an earthquake. These will lead to significant geotechnical damage to the embankment foundation. Thus, proper mitigating measures should be provided in order to make sure that the soil foundation where the road embankment will be built is strong enough to withstand any failures, like seismic liquefaction.

Specific Objective 5:

Develop an appropriate mitigation plan to address the soil liquefaction hazard impacting the embankment foundation.

Mitigation

The presence of a liquefiable soil layer within the study area posed a significant risk to the road embankment foundation. To address the soil liquefaction hazard, a ground improvement technique is necessary to conduct and implement in the area. There are different classifications of ground improvement methods, which include compaction, reinforcement, ground replacement, grouting, and chemical modification. These methods have their own specific advantage in terms of improving the soil condition, but it has also have some limitations. The effectiveness of these ground improvement methods will depend on both the soil material and the target depth of improvement. The time, cost, process, and equipment for each method were also included in the mitigation plan to determine the most cost-effective method against soil liquefaction.

The ground improvement technique that is cost-effective and most economical to use in the study area is the soil reinforcement method. These methods include the application of a stone column and geosynthetic material to the area (Figure 6). These two methods of reinforcement are technically suitable for sand, silt, and clay material. The stone columns are installed using a vibrating probe, which is inserted in the ground and fills the hole with coarse aggregate. The resulting columns work through a combination of three key mechanisms: densification, drainage, and reinforcement. During the installation, the vibrating probe rearranges and compacts the surrounding soil, increasing the soil's density, making it more resistant to liquefaction. Since the stones or gravel are highly permeable, they act as a vertical drainage, which allows excess pore water pressure to dissipate quickly during seismic shaking, preventing the soil from losing its strength, which directly addresses the root cause of liquefaction. Furthermore, the stone columns are generally stiffer and stronger than the surrounding soil, which provides reinforcement and overall stability to the soil material.

Figure 6. Stone Column Installation

In addition, combining the stone column with a geosynthetic layer such as geogrid or geotextile offers a high-performance platform for the embankment foundation (Figure 7). Encasing the stone column with geosynthetic material prevents the migration of fines into the column, which ensures that the drainage capacity remains effective during seismic events. Furthermore, it also provides uniform load distribution to the surrounding soil, reduces the damaging differential settlement, confines the soil to increase its resistance to shear forces during earthquake shaking, and reinforces the soil to prevent lateral spreading and large deformation. Thus, the application of these two reinforcement methods creates a highly effective and robust ground improvement system for liquefaction mitigation.

Figure 7. Geosynthetic Reinforced Column Supported Embankment

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study, it was concluded the following:

1. The earthquake-induced parameters classified in the research study include the site geological data, tectonics and seismicity data, geotechnical borehole data, and geometric design of the embankment foundation. The study area lies within the Quaternary Alluvium. The unconsolidated alluvial deposits were considered to be susceptible to liquefaction due to their loose and relatively young age structure. The nearest active fault within the study area is the West Valley Fault. The said fault system will generate a peak ground acceleration of 0.4053 g for a 7.5 earthquake magnitude. Moreover, the geotechnical borehole data show that the study area is composed of interlayering of sand, silt, and clay. The loose saturated coarse-grained material and fine-grained material whose plasticity index is <18 and WC/LL of <0.80 are considered to be moderately to highly susceptible to liquefaction. Furthermore, one of the contributing factors in the soil-foundation interaction is the geometric design of the embankment foundation. The performance of the foundation will depend primarily on its dimensions, structural loads, and ground pressure exerted on the soil. The

measured cross-sectional area of the embankment is 252 m² having a total weight load of 47,880 kN and ground pressure of 190 $\frac{\text{kN}}{\text{m}^2}$.

2. The geotechnical borehole data, together with the laboratory test results, were used as an input parameter in the SPT-based liquefaction triggering method to determine the cyclic stress ratio and cyclic resistance ratio of the soil. The computed CSR value in the study area ranges from 0.2584 to 0.4732, while the CRR value ranges from 0.1186 to 4.0593. The resulting data provides insights into how the soil will respond during an earthquake. In the analysis, three (3) factors generally affect the CSR value. This includes the peak ground acceleration (PGA), stress reduction factor, and the effective stress of the soil. When the PGA value increases, the CSR value also increases. Furthermore, the factor that the CRR value is highly dependent on was the corrected SPT N-values of the soil. A general trend of a decrease in stress reduction factor and CSR value, while increasing in corrected SPT N-values, effective vertical stress, and CRR values, was observed as we go deeper into the soil. This indicates that at greater depths, the lower the chances for the soil to experience liquefaction.
3. The factor of safety provides insights into whether the soil in the study area is vulnerable to liquefaction under a given seismic scenario. A minimum FS value of 1.25 was adopted to quantify the variability in the soil parameters. In the assessment, the FS value that is lower than the acceptable value of 1.25 was calculated on the upper portion of the borehole. It ranges from 0.2507 to 1.0010. Moreover, a higher FS value was measured at greater depths. The increase in the FS value is primarily due to a higher CRR value calculated at the bottom portion of the borehole. This observation implies that the bottom soil layer has a higher soil resistance against liquefaction than the upper soil layer.
4. The depth of the liquefiable soil layer in the study area is measured to be from 0.0 m NGL to 6.0 m NGL. The thickness of this liquefiable soil layer is around 3.0 m to 4.5 m, wherein the thickest layer was observed in BH-01 and BH-03. The soil material corresponding to this depth includes clayey sand, sandy silt, and elastic silt having low SPT N-values and a plasticity index. The low SPT N-values and plasticity index indicate that the soil is prone to collapse and does not have enough cohesive strength to resist liquefaction. These make these soil layers highly susceptible to liquefaction. Moreover, to better understand the geotechnical performance of the embankment foundation when these soil layer liquefies, different factors like the induced upward total buoyant force, modulus of subgrade reaction, differential displacement, and tilting were determined. The calculated induced upward total buoyant force was in the range of 7,416.36 kN to 11,124.54 kN. These range values were greater than the net downward force, which indicates that the embankment foundation will not experience uplift during seismic shaking. The measured modulus of subgrade reaction ranges from 1665.72 kPa/m to 2658.60 kPa/m. The lowest modulus of subgrade reaction was observed in BH-03. The low subgrade modulus of reaction value indicates that the soil material is highly compressible and lacks stiffness to provide adequate support for the foundation. Furthermore, the computed differential displacement and tilting of the embankment foundation range from 1.13 m to 1.36 m and 4.08° to 4.89°. In a worst-case scenario, the embankment

foundation will experience tilting up to 4.89° and will be displaced to a maximum depth of 1.36 m. This will result in significant geotechnical damage to the road embankment foundation.

5. Mitigating measures against soil liquefaction should be implemented within the study area. This can be done by conducting a ground improvement technique on the subsurface soil layer that will liquefy during seismic shaking. Different methods of improvement were considered in the mitigation plan. This includes compaction, reinforcement, ground replacement, grouting, and chemical modification. The selection of which methods will be used is primarily based on the soil material and the target depth of ground improvement. The soil material in the study area is characterized by interlayered sand, silt, and clay with a high percentage of fines. Due to the soil conditions of having high fines content and plasticity, if the compaction method is used as the technique for improvement, some of the layers will not be compacted, as this method is usually underperformed when the fines content exceeds about 15–20%. Moreover, the grouting method is also less reliable to use as the fine particles can block the grout's flow, preventing it from permeating the entire soil mass, which will result in an uneven and ineffective treatment. The ground replacement method is also insignificant to use as removing and replacing the 4.5 m thick layer of liquefiable material will require extensive labor and a large quantity of fill material, which later on will still need to be treated. The chemical modification can be effective for soil stabilization in the study area; however, these methods are significantly expensive, and the improvement method requires careful mixing, a specific amount of binder, and a curing period for it to become stable. The ground improvement technique that is technically cost-effective and most economical to use in the study area is the soil reinforcement method, which involves the installation of stone columns and geosynthetic materials. This method is highly applicable to both coarse-grained soil and fine-grained soil. The stone columns provide adequate densification, drainage, and reinforcement to the liquefiable soil layer. The stone columns densify and reinforce the soil material by rearranging the soil particles during installation, which makes it stiffer, denser, and stronger, leading to more resistance to liquefaction. In addition, encasing the stone column with geosynthetic material prevents the migration of fines into the column. This makes the drainage capacity of the stone columns remain effective during seismic events. The vertical drainage allows excess pore water pressure to dissipate quickly during seismic shaking, preventing the soil from losing its strength, which directly addresses the root cause of liquefaction. Thus, the soil reinforcement method will provide a high-performance platform for the embankment foundation.

Recommendations

Based on the results of the study conducted, the following are recommended:

1. Conduct additional borehole drilling within the study area. These boreholes should be strategically located between the existing boreholes. As the existing six (6) boreholes are located widely spaced from one another, variabilities in terms of different soil profiles and data parameters are expected. The additional

boreholes help to minimize these variabilities in soil data. The more closely spaced the boreholes, the more accurate the results will be.

2. Integrate the use of probabilistic methods in the soil liquefaction assessment. The probabilistic analysis quantifies the uncertainties and variabilities in the data parameter. Unlike the deterministic method, which provides only a single value result, the probabilistic methods provide a full range of possible values, where the certainty of the results is explicitly shown. Moreover, since both the probabilistic method and the deterministic method are industry-accepted methods, combining these two methods provides precise and reliable results.
3. Implement a ground improvement technique as mitigation to soil liquefaction. The reinforcement method, utilizing a stone column encased in geosynthetic material, is recommended as the primary countermeasure against soil liquefaction in the study area. The stone column should be installed to a design depth of up to ten (10) meters into the subsurface soil layer, with a spacing of approximately 1.5 m to 3.0 m. This design plan will provide adequate densification and reinforcement to the surrounding soil and better drainage capacity for the excess pore water pressure to dissipate quickly during seismic shaking.
4. Perform a numerical modeling analysis using a geotechnical Finite Element Method (FEM) software prior to the actual installation of the stone column. The modeling software provides an initial assessment that visualizes and validates the performance of the stone column in an actual field scenario. The results of the analysis will also quantify how much is the improvement of the liquefiable soil layer beneath the embankment foundation by means of the increase in soil density and drainage capacity.

REFERENCES

- [1] Lou, A., Casibua, D., Dizon, M. A. P., Ledesma, M. M., & Acacio, A. P. A. (2019). Evaluation of liquefaction potential on the reclamation area of Manila Bay.
- [2] Naghizadehrokni, M., Choobbasti, A. J., & Naghizadehrokni, M. (2018a). Liquefaction maps in Babol City, Iran, through probabilistic and deterministic approaches. *Geoenvironmental Disasters*, 5(1), 1–17. <https://doi.org/10.1186/S40677-017-0094-9/FIGURES/11>
- [3] Goharzay, M., Noorzad, A., Ardakani, A. M., & Jalal, M. (2017). A worldwide SPT-based soil liquefaction triggering analysis utilizing gene expression programming and Bayesian probabilistic method. *Journal of Rock Mechanics and Geotechnical Engineering*, 9(4), 683–693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/J.JRMGE.2017.03.011>
- [4] Youd, T. L., & Idriss, I. M. (2001a). Liquefaction Resistance of Soils: Summary Report from the 1996 NCEER and 1998 NCEERNSF Workshops on Evaluation of Liquefaction Resistance of Soils. *Journal of Geotechnical and Geoenvironmental Engineering*, 127(4), 297–313. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)1090-0241\(2001\)127:4\(297\)](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)1090-0241(2001)127:4(297))